

THE INFLUENCE OF FUZZY CONTROL ON THE EQUIPMENT USED FOR THE GROWTH OF POROUS SEMICONDUCTORS FILMS

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ABSTRACT

There was designed the hardware of the Semiconductors porous film growth; it is characterised by the application of the fuzzy controller, which is based on the empirical rules that establish the relationship between current, voltage, temperature, solution composition and parameters of the Semiconductors porous film, which allows to obtain a porous semiconductor with specified properties. Based on the results of the system analysis, it can be argued that the use of the fuzzy expert system for automatic control of the equipment for growing of porous semiconductors films will ensure adequate determination of the required anodising current without operator intervention or use of the SCADA system.

Keywords: SCADA system, porous, semiconductors, fuzzy controller.

Introduction. The main trends in the development of electronics are related to the increasing of functional complexity of electrical devices. These devices are becoming faster and more sensitive. These requirements determine the direction in which we are working to find new materials and new technological processes which could provide the required quality indicators [1].

Recently, researchers have shown great interest in the properties of composite materials. Composite materials are made up of many interconnected nanoscale particles.

The properties of nanoparticles differ significantly from the properties of the materials from which they are formed. The main factors of property modification include:

- 1) the confinement of charge carrier motion in particles whose size is comparable to the de Broglie wavelength for electrons and holes, the so-called quantum dimensional effect, which causes changes in electronic properties, such as width of the band gap;
- 2) the highly developed surface that nanocomposite media can have (as a consequence), the adsorption of molecules on the surface leads to the emergence of new properties, both electronic and optical;
- 3) modification of the electromagnetic fields acting on each atom of the medium in comparison with bulk materials.

Porous Semiconductors has been identified as a potentially effective material which could be used for low penetrating dislocations and strains and for the

growth of epitaxial layers[2-4].

Obtaining films of porous Semiconductors with high pore density is considered as difficult task. However, with the rapid development of manufacturing technology, it is now possible to achieve a high quality porous Semiconductors structure in much simpler and less expensive way. Electrochemical etching using a suitable electrolyte solution is one possible method.

Porous semiconductors is used in electronic devices, light emitting devices and can be used for humidity sensors, gas, chemical and biological sensors, and for photo-dynamic therapy [5-7].

Materials and methods of research. An electrochemical cell for the optimal cultivation of porous Semiconductors is not as simple design as it might appear at first glance, and there are many technical challenges to overcome during its development.

Firstly, the etching of Semiconductors requires aggressive electrolytes. The ever-present RF places severe constraints on materials and electrodes.

Secondly, the process often requires illumination. This means that the etching cell must have a window.

Thirdly, porous films intended for use in real devices must meet strict requirements for homogeneity and reproducibility of film parameters [8].

Looking at a relatively simple design without electrode comparison, with illumination as an option, it is necessary to consider a single or double cell configuration, as schematically shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Electrolytic cells for the production of a porous layer: a) single-cell configuration b) double-cell configuration (1 - PVC bath; 2 - electrolyte; 3 - sample; 4 - ohmic contact; 5 - platinum electrode; 6 - quartz window; 7 - sealing ring; 8 - porous layer; arrows indicate direction of illumination)

The absence of a backside metallisation eliminates the potential source of sample contamination in any subsequent thermal and chemical treatment; the absence of metal on the backside may simply be necessary for thermal treatment. However, there are drawbacks, for example with Semiconductors etching, the electrolyte on the backside is reversed and therefore does not allow significant electrical current. This problem can be solved by exposing the back side, or by using a high p^+ such as Semiconductors, which draws large reverse currents already at low potentials. Formation of p^+ or n^- on n^- p^- substrates, respectively, using ion implantation followed by annealing is the best way to do this [9].

The range of research have shown that the position and geometry of the electrode also has a major effect on the homogeneity of the pore-Semiconductors layer. If a platinum mesh is used, the total surface area should be comparable to that of the por-Semiconductors electrode and the mesh hole size should be smaller than the distance to the por-Semiconductors electrode. Better homogeneity around the centre can be achieved by increasing the size of the sample and cathode.

The graphite plate is electrically connected to the sample, which allows the improvement of quality in both lateral and vertical uniformity of the por-Semiconductors layer, even at low current densities $j=2$ mA/cm².

It should also be noted that the process of dissolving Semiconductors, especially in aqueous electrolytes, always produces hydrogen and the resulting hydrogen bubbles can adhere to the plate surface and cause a change in the local potential. Bubbles adhering to the surface of the sample can cause pore degeneration. In any case, hydrogen bubbles can cause significant inhomogeneity of pore-Semiconductors parameters, either

in the lateral direction or in the depth of the pore-Semiconductors layer, and should be avoided. Such approach to the design of an electrochemical pickling chamber for industrial production is used by Bosch GmbH.

The anodising tool to be used in mass production must have the following attributes: safety and environmental protection, compatibility, reliability and quality.

The concentration of 15-40% HF is a kind of standard for the production of micro- and mesoporous layers.

Cathodic polarisation, for both n-type and p-type materials, Semiconductors is stable. The cathodic reaction of water reduction at the Semiconductors/HF interface with the formation of hydrogen gas is important.

At high anode overloads, surface electropolishing of Semiconductors occurs and the surface retains a smooth and flat morphology. In contrast, at low anode overloads, the surface morphology is dominated by a large maze of channels penetrating deep into the sample. It is only under these conditions that porous Semiconductors is formed.

Results and discussion. Numerous studies have shown that the composition of the electrolyte has a strong influence on the formation of the porous layer (structure, thickness, porosity) in the anodising process. Increasing the concentration of hydrofluoric acid leads to a decrease in porosity and pore diameter [10].

On the basis of these studies, it is possible to formulate a table of the dependence of the porosity of the semiconductor layer on the concentration of HF (Table 1).

Table 1

Porosity of semiconductor layer as a function of HF								
HF (%)	8	10	11.5	13	14.5	16.5	17.5	19.5
Porosity (%)	1	23	65	73	62	58	55	35

Based on the study of the dependence of the required porosity of the semiconductor film, a set of productive rules for the fuzzy expert system can be formulated and the terms of linguistic variables can be determined. The operation of the fuzzy system was verified by modelling in the MatLab/Fuzzy Logic Toolbox package.

It is most appropriate to feed the control system with information about the composition of the electrolyte solution, the electrolyte temperature, the voltage and the desired film thickness. Accordingly, the values of these indicators will be the main input linguistic var-

tables. The result of the calculation of the fuzzy inference algorithm is the recommended value of the anodizing current.

The output signal Por_sys1 is calculated using the Sugeno algorithm of the 0th order.

- The settings have the following parameters:
- FIS Name - Por_sys1; FIS Type - sugeno;
 - And method - prod; Or method - probor;
 - Implication - min; Aggregation - max;

- Defuzzification - wtaver.
- This system consists of four input parameters:
- temperature of the hydrofluoric acid solution C, C⁰;
 - hydrofluoric acid concentration HF(%), %;
 - tension - U(B), B;
 - desired porosity - %.
- The output signal OUT is the anodization current. The setting of the constants is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Setting the output signal constants					
Amperage(mA)	0	10	20	40	60
Name of the constant	ZERO	SMALL	MID	HIGH	MAX

The research work was carried out on the basis the Siemens automation system laboratory. During the design stage, the block diagram, which is shown in Fig. 2, was synthesised.

The system consists of the following main elements:

- 1) Cell for porous layers etching, which consists of:
 - a) clamps;
 - b) clamp pins;
 - c) fluoroplastic cell;
 - d) electrolytic concentrate;
 - e) insulating substrate;
 - f) plate (Semiconductors sample);

- g) ohmic electrode;
- i) tripod;
- j) platinum electrode;
- k) digital temperature sensor.
- 2) PLC (programmable logic controller) SIEMENS S7-1500;
- 3) digital signal input module;
- 4) Siemens KTP700 Basic graphic touch panel of the operator;
- 5) modular programmable power supply NI PXI-4132;
- 6) network hub;
- 7) personal computer.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the fuzzy control system for growing of a russet layer

The electrochemical cell is made of fluoroplastic with an NI PXI-4132 modular programmable power supply. The NI PXI-4132 module has two isolated output channels, one providing a voltage output from 0 to

+100 V and the other from 0 to -100 V. Both channels provide up to 1 A of output current. All channels provide up to 1 A of output current.

The module provides 16-bit output voltage and current settings. The module has RS232/RS485/USB/Ethernet communication interfaces. A Symaro QFA3160D digital temperature sensor is used to measure the temperature of the electrolyte solution in the range -400 to $+700$ C. This sensor "communicates" with the Siemens S7-1500 PLC via digital data input module, and the Siemens KTP700 Basic graphic touch panel is used to control the growing process.

The touch panel and PLC are programmed via the network hub using the Ethernet communication interface.

After modelling the system operation and synthesising the structural scheme of the porous semiconductor film growing system, the PLC and operator panel were programmed using the TIA-Portal V13 software component to study the operation of the fuzzy expert system. To carry out the calculation of the degree in the

TIA-Portal V13 software environment, the "CALCULATE" block was used.

The input "IN(x)" is any variable;

The output "OUT" displays the value after calculation.

To calculate the function of the terms "B" and "C", the etching voltage, and the terms "MID" and "HIGH", the film porosity, the following steps were performed:

OUT:=(IN3-IN2)/(IN2-IN1); and assigned the tag "m_voltage";

OUT:=(IN2-IN3)/(IN1-IN3); and assigned the tag "m1_voltage";

OUT:=(IN2-IN3)/(IN1-IN3); and assigned the tag "m_porus";

OUT:=(IN3-IN2)/(IN2-IN1); and assigned the tag "m1_porus".

The application of these blocks in the TIA Portal V13 software component is shown in Fig.3.a-d.

Fig. 3. Application of the "CALCULATE" block in the TIA-Portal V13 environment: a) U(B) term "B"; b) U(B) term "C"; c) POR(%) term "MID"; d) POR(%) term "HIGH".

"MIN" compares the values of two or more parameters IN1 ÷ IN(n) and assigns the minimum (smaller) value to the OUT parameter;

"MAX" compares the values of the two parameters IN1 ÷ IN(n) and assigns the maximum (greater) value to the OUT parameter.

For each rule, the "MIN" command is used and a tag is assigned:

"m2" - 1st rule (output is ZERO); (Fig. 4.a)

"m3" - 2nd rule (output is SMALL); (Fig. 4.b)

"m4" - 3rd rule (output is MID); (Fig. 4.c)

"m5" - 4th rule (output is HIGH); (Fig. 4.d)

"m6" - 5th rule (output is MAX); (Fig. 4.e)

If the output of the rules is the same, in this case, for example, of the 3rd and the 5th, it is necessary to

select a greater value for it, using the command "MAX" COMMAND (Fig. 4.f).

For defuzzification, a simplified formula for the center of gravity is used, in this case:

$$OUT = \frac{m2 \times a1 \times m3 \times a4 \times m3 \times a3 \times m5 \times a2}{a1 + a2 + a3 + a4} \quad (1)$$

To calculate the output, the "CALCULATE" block is used, which contains an expression: $OUT := (IN1 * IN5 + IN2 * IN6 + IN3 * IN7 + IN4 * IN8) / (IN1 + IN2 + IN3 + IN4)$ and assigned the tag "Recommended_Current" (Fig. 5).

After that, the developed software was compiled and written to a Siemens PLC.

Fig. 4. Application of the "MIN" and "MAX" commands in the TIA Portal V13 programming language: a-1st rule; b-2nd rule; c-3rd rule; d-4th rule; e-5th rule; f-6th rule; g-7th rule; h-8th rule; i-9th rule; e-5th rule; f-3rd and 5th rule

Fig. 5. Defuzzification and calculation of recommended anodising current

After compiling and running the system, the indicators were taken, which made it possible to compare them with the values of the outputs of the MatLab/Fuzzy Logic Toolbox fuzzy system (shown in Table 3 and Fig. 6).

Table 1.3

Experimental study of the system operation

Indicator	C, C ⁰	HF, %	U, B	POR, % (мод)	POR, % (експ)	OUT, ma
Value	-5	8	2	1	2	10
	10	13	7	23	24	20
	20	20	20	45	43	30
	30	40	25	68	70	40
	30	40	70	78	75	0,05
	40	35	2	70	71	15

Comparing the simulated values (POR, % (mod)) and the experimental values (POR, % (exp)), we can see that the average discrepancy reaches ±2%.

Fig. 6. Plots of the etching time of the broken film during system operation

Interval “A” is the pore formation, “B” is the transition area and “C” is the end of the programme before polishing.

The morphology of the films was studied using an NT-MDT Ntegra Therna scanning probe microscope. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show 3D images. (a, b, c) and 2D images (a, b, c), respectively, of the surface of the studied films grown under the above conditions. Note that at the current density 1 mA/cm^2 time The digestion time reached 40 minutes, at 15 mA/cm^2 – 20 min, at 25 mA/cm^2 – 15 min.

Fig. 1.7. 3D SEM images of porous film samples obtained under different conditions: a) $j = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$; b) $j = 15 \text{ mA/cm}^2$; c) $j = 25 \text{ mA/cm}^2$

Fig. 1.8. 2D SEM images of porous film samples obtained under different conditions: a) $j = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$; b) $j = 15 \text{ mA/cm}^2$; c) $j = 25 \text{ mA/cm}^2$

Conclusions. The work presents the new solution for the urgent scientific and applied problem and is aimed at improvement of the model for formation of control influences of a Semiconductors porous film growing unit through application of the fuzzy controller, which allows to obtain the porous semiconductor with specified properties. Based on the results of our research, the following can be stated.

Furthermore, the calculation tables describing the dependence on the composition of the hydrofluoric acid solution, temperature and voltage were obtained, which allowed to control the program and to determine the parameters of the electrolysis current and the conditions till the end of the process of the porous film growing.

The fuzzy control software module was config and optimised.

There was designed the hardware of the Semiconductors porous film growth; it is characterised by the application of the fuzzy controller, which is based on the empirical rules that establish the relationship between current, voltage, temperature, solution composition and parameters of the Semiconductors porous film, which allows to obtain a porous semiconductor with specified properties.

During the research work the software implementation of the graphical user interface for a fuzzy control system for the growth parameters of porous semiconductors films was carried out.

The tools used for development of the control programs for industrial programmable controllers TIA Portal V13 in the basic set do not contain special modules for the implementation of fuzzy systems. In the course of the research we developed programming procedures in IEC 61131 standard, which for the selected configuration of the fuzzy system implement the simplified logical inference algorithm and correspond to the MatLab model with an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$.

Conclusions. 1. the methods, techniques and equipment used in the process of growing of porous semiconductors films and the requirements for the main properties have been analysed.

2. It was also synthesised the model of a fuzzy control system for the equipment designed to grow porous semiconductors films based on the analysis of parameters, the study of basic methods and equipment for the growth of porous semiconductor films.

3. In addition, the structure of a fuzzy control system for controlling the growing parameters of porous semiconductors films was synthesised.

4. There was investigated the adequacy of the control program mod-ules and the fuzzy logic control was implemented in the laboratory complex.

5. Based on the results of the system analysis, it can be argued that the use of the fuzzy expert system for automatic control of the equipment for growing of porous semiconductors films will ensure adequate determination of the required anodising current without operator intervention or use of the SCADA system. The equipment for controlling the parameters of growing of porous semiconductors films meets the requirements for studying the influence of parameters on the thickness, nature and structure of porous semiconductor films.

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